

THE CONCEPTS OF “COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE” AND “GAMIFICATION OF ENGLISH LEARNING FOR SPECIAL PURPOSE” IN SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE

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Abstract

The article defines the essence of the concepts of “competence” and “competence in learning”. These concepts’ understanding by different researchers is highlighted, differences and similarities of these concepts definition by scientists are shown. The concepts of “communicative competence” and “professional communicative competence” are defined, their features are outlined. Our study also examines the problem of losing interest in the learning as one of the main issues of modern pedagogy, analyzes a relatively new motivation tool “gamification”. The definitions of this concept by different researchers are given. It is highlighted that the most appropriate one is the usage of gaming practices and mechanisms in a non-gaming context to engage users to solve different problems. It is also noted that to solve the problem of the effectiveness of professional training, the use of the gamification approach in learning the maritime English for professional purpose is proposed during the creation of e-courses in the system of blended education, which involves the harmonious combination of traditional learning and online learning using e-learning environment. In our research we consider the gamification approach in the informational and educational environment. In our article the advantages of using the gamification approach comparing to other approaches are also outlined.

Keywords: communicative competence, gamification, English for professional purpose, e-courses, blended learning.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5571.2018.00803

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1. Introduction

Nowadays the growing trend in higher education is the rapid development of modern technologies. Pedagogical technologies are primarily aimed at the formation of a competent specialist, competitive in the global labor market.

The scientists of many countries have been studying the problem of training a competent specialist (mobile, able to quickly orient in the trends of refinement and upgrade equipment, understand the principles of their work and the rules of service, with the ability to learn). The concept of “communicative competence” was the subject of research of various disciplines [1]. For example, pedagogy aims to raise competencies to form an independent and responsible activity was systematically described in the works of the domestic scientists [2]. We suppose that the most systematic materials of the research are reflected in the works about the actual problem of formation of communicative activity of students of higher educational institutions [3]. But domestic scientists didn’t connect communicative competence formation with gamification. The foreign scholars, who explored the possibility of introducing a competent approach to the teaching of students and cadets, using gamification approach, proved that the learner moves forward from an introverted mode of shyness and becomes more motivated based on positive feedback and used game elements. Gamification is analyzed as one of the trends to form communicative competence of students. Though there were no explanation of “competence” and “communicative competence” concepts [4].

The objectives of our research are: to define and specify the essence of the concepts of “competence” and “competence in learning”, “communicative competence” and “professional communicative competence”; to analyze these concepts’ understanding by different researchers; to analyze a relatively new motivation tool “gamification”.

2. Methods

To solve the problems set in the study, we used following interrelated methods:

Theoretical: terminological analysis - to determine the basic concepts of the study “competence”, “communicative competence”, “competence in learning”, “gamification approach”; analy-

sis, comparison of these concepts by different researchers; synthesis, generalization of theoretical positions, normative documents, and experience of teaching the communicative language of future ship engineers to determine the most appropriate approaches to the problem;

Statistical: methods of mathematical statistics for the purpose of analysis of experimental data of the study and their interpretations.

Methodological: competency approach – to determine the target indicators of professional English training; systematic approach – study of the training of future ship engineers as a complex system; gamification approach – the use of a game mechanic in non-gaming processes.

3. Results

Professional training is focused on the formation of a competent specialist who uses the acquired knowledge to solve specific practical tasks in professional activities. The concepts of “competence”, “communicative competence” and “professional competence” in scientific discourse were identified and specified (**Table 1**).

Table 1

The concepts of “competence”, “communicative competence” and “professional competence” in scientific discourse

Concept	Author	Definition
1	2	3
competent	Russian dictionary of I. Ozhegov	a knowledgeable, well-informed, authoritative in a particular field [4]
competent	«New Explanatory Dictionary of the Ukrainian Language»	who has sufficient knowledge in any field; who is well aware of something; clever; which is based on knowledge; qualified.
competence	Russian researcher Shishov	an ability to act on the basis of the acquired knowledge
competence	Professor Y. Rubin	a set of competencies (personal qualities of a specialist to solve a certain type of professional tasks)
competence	M. Leontyan	the result of acquiring competences
competence	F. Sharipov	a set of features (characteristics) of a person that allows him to perform qualitatively certain activities aimed at solving problems in a particular field [5]
competence	A. Aronov	the readiness of a specialist to engage in certain activities
competence	Experts of the DeSeCo project	the ability to successfully meet individual and social needs and perform the tasks [6]
competency	the International Board of Standards for Training, Performances and Instruction	the ability to perform qualifications, perform tasks, or work in a qualified manner
competence in learning	The Encyclopedia of Education	a quality acquired by a young person not only during the study of an object, a group of subjects, but also through means of non-formal education, due to the influence of the environment etc.
competence in learning	International organizations (European Commission, UNESCO)	the ability to apply knowledge and skills that provides for the active use of educational achievements in new situations
professional competence	T. Khlebnikov	a conglomeration of components: a special (professional skills at a high level), social (ability to cooperate, communicate, realize social responsibility), personal (possession of methods of personal self-expression and self-development) and individual one (readiness for professional growth)
professional competence	P. Lerner	an integral characteristic that determines the ability of the individual to solve professional problems and typical problems using knowledge and abilities
professional competence	Ukrainian Wikipedia	the ability to use knowledge, skills, experience in specific circumstances, while achieving the most positive result
professional competence	psychological dictionary	a successful professional activity, its significance and certain specific tasks in combination with all the knowledge and skills used in its implementation

1	2	3
standard of competence	International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watch-keeping for Seafarers (STCW)	the level of professional training that must be achieved for the proper performance of the functions of the ship in accordance with criteria agreed at the international level and includes prescribed standards or levels of knowledge, understanding and demonstrated skills
communicative competence	I. Zimna	competence concerning the interaction of man with other people
communicative competence	L. Guzeev	the ability to engage in communication for the sake of understanding
communicative competence	K. Khoruzhenko	a person's preparedness for cultural communication with other people
communicative competence	David and Julia Jary	a communicative ability (the ways in which people communicate with others in the community through communicative exchanges and interactions) [7]
communicative competence	Ukrainian Wikipedia	the ability of the individual to apply in a concrete communication, language knowledge, ways of interaction with surrounding and distant people and events, skills of work in a group, possession of various social roles
communicative competence	social psychology	the ability to establish and maintain the necessary contacts with other people, a certain set of knowledge, skills that provide effective communication
communicative competence	Y. Fedorenko	knowledge and skills in the branches of linguistics
communicative competence	V. Krylova	an integral, relatively stable, psychological entity, manifested in individual psychological, personality characteristics in the behavior and communication of a particular individual

Modern pedagogical technologies often use electronic game techniques to diversify learning, enhance motivation, etc. The concept of "gamification" was specified (**Table 2**).

Table 2
The concept of "gamification" in scientific discourse

Author	Definition
1	2
Ukrainian Wikipedia	the use of gaming practices and mechanisms in a non-gaming context to attract end-users to solve different problems
Russian Wikipedia	an application of approaches typical of computer games in software tools for non-gaming processes. It is a complex of motivational managerial techniques borrowed from computer games and their creators
Professor of Legal Studies and Business Ethics at The Wharton School, University of Pennsylvania Kevin Werbach	complex of motivational managerial techniques borrowed from computer games and their creators (medals, badges, points, and other attributes of virtual victories) [7]
the author of the concept of «Gamification in Business» G. Zickermann	a process of using the gaming mechanism and thinking in order to increase the audience and solve problems [8]
Professor of Instructional Technology, Bloomsburg University K. Kapp	the implementation of the principles of game mechanics and thinking in order to attract people to an active learning process, to motivate and solve different problems
K. Robson	the application of the principles of developing games in non-edgy contexts and can be used in business
Umar Ruhi	a process of using a digital platform for the inclusion of gaming elements in non-contextual contexts in order to positively influence the motivation of the user and improve the interaction of users with the desired behavior in the educational environment

1	2
J. Sanders, Manager of Innovation at Deloitte Consulting	a technology that captures the essence of gaming and applies them to a range of real processes inside the organization, including training and development, rather than for entertainment [9]
Researcher S. Deterding from Hamburg University	a trend that combines a large number of existing concepts and research in the field of people-to-computer interaction and gaming research, such as serious games, popular games, virtual reality games, or game design
V. Kukharengo	a technique for changing human behavior, since it is based on an analysis of human behavior, as well as a methodology of correct motivation, which is based on the analysis of the behavior of this person and is increasingly used in education, which will help to give students very important tools to achieve victories in real life

In our study, we considered the gamification approach in e-environment as a transformation of non-gaming material to enhance motivation, extend the term of interest in solving professional problems, and increase the likelihood of achieving its goal, through the prism of advanced technologies for the formation of English- language professional communicative competence, namely knowledge, skills and abilities that determine the success of communicative activities for solving future professional problems by ship engineers.

4. Discussion

The use of gamification approach (game-like activities, scoreboards, points, badges etc.) to form professional communicative competence of future ship engineers is effective because of the deep motivation, embedded in a competitive environment, a psychological aspect that allows the student to feel imaginary control, to know at what level he is and where he needs to go.

Gamification approach also encourages good behavior-progress, tasks, etc. Another powerful psychological driving factor in student's behavior is the system of achievements that gamification approach enjoys. As a result of this approach, students receive strong positive emotions, such as excitement. All these factors outline the gamification approach as one of the newest effective teaching methods in forming communicative competence. The results of our study are used in creation of e-courses in LMS MOODLE of Kherson State Maritime Academy (subject – English for specific purpose). The same positive results were fully described in the research of usage gamification to enhance second language learning process. The scientist proved that each game element, used in Gamification, enhances automatically the teaching and learning process of the students [9]. These results of gamification usage in studying process were also proved by the Motivation-oriented Scenario-based Gamification Design Method. The researcher proved that compared with the previous studies in gamification design framework and method, this study is more effective one [10].

Prospects for further developments we see in the consideration of other innovative approaches to the formation of a communicative English competence of the future maritime industry specialists.

5. Conclusions

1. The essence of the concepts of “competence”, “competence in learning”, “communicative competence” and “professional communicative competence” were defined. These concepts' understanding by different researchers (Ozhegov, Shishov, Rubin, Leontyan, Sharipov, Aronov, Khlebnikov, Zimna, Guzeev, Khoruzhenko, Fedorenko, Krylova and others) was highlighted, differences and similarities of these concepts definition by scientists were shown.

2. The concept of “gamification” was defined, its features were outlined. The definitions of this concept by different researchers (Werbach, Zickermann, Kapp, Robson, Umar Ruhi, Sanders, Deterding, Kukharengo and others) were given. Our study also examined the problem of losing interest in the learning as one of the main issues of modern pedagogy, analyzed “gamification”.

2. It was proved that the most appropriate tool is the usage of gaming practices and mechanisms in a non-gaming context to engage users to solve different problems.

3. It was also proved that to solve the problem of the effectiveness of professional training, the use of the gamification approach in learning the maritime English for professional purpose gives positive results. Gamification usage was proposed during the creation of e-courses in the system of blended education.

4. In our research the advantages of using the gamification approach comparing to other approaches were also outlined.

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